

WASTE 4think

MOVING TOWARDS LIFE CYCLE THINKING BY INTEGRATING ADVANCED WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

The Zamudio pilot will
implement different activities:

"OPERATION and PLANNING TOOLS"

A full monitoring of dustbins
and lorries and a decision
taking information system

To reduce waste generation and
improve the reuse and recycling
rate

"CITIZEN SCIENCE"

Open Educational
Resources (OER)

Serious
Games

Innovative awareness and
waste prevention campaigns

ZAMUDIO

as well as...

Implementation of
new economic
instruments (Pay-as-
you-Throw 'PAYT')

ICT tools (Apps)

To involve all possible agents responsible for waste generation

Identify new business and governance models

"ORGANIC WASTE COLLECTION"

For valorisation of these high-value resources

in Schools, industrial area and Town Hall

"ZERO WASTE ECOSYSTEMS"

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